

Oxidative Studies on *trans*-(3-Phenyl-2-propenyl)phenols and 2-Methoxy-4-(2-propenyl)phenol and 2-Methoxy-4-(1-propenyl)phenol

MEERA R. IYER, S. BASKARAN and GIRISH K. TRIVEDI*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Powai, Bombay-400 076

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Oxidative reaction on *trans*-2-(3-phenyl-2-propenyl)phenols (1-4) and *para*-alkenylphenols have been studied. The products formed include benzofurane (5-8) and neolignane (16-18).

Quinone methides are considered to be biological intermediates in the biosynthesis of several naturally occurring phenolic compounds that include lignin and 8.0.4' neolignans¹. They have been reported to be the key intermediates in anthrahydroquinone catalysed delignification of wood under alkaline pulping conditions². The quinone methides therefore serve as useful intermediates in the biomimetic synthesis of several natural substances.

During the course of studies on the palladium(II) and silver(I) catalysed oxidation of α,β - and β,γ -*para*-alkenylphenols, involvement of the respective quinone methide intermediates have been noticed³. Encouraged by the results, oxidative reactions of alkenyl phenols have been further studied. The present communication describes the results obtained during the oxidation of *trans*-2-(3-phenyl-2-propenyl)phenols (1-4) and eugenol (11) and isoeugenol (12) with palladium(II) chloride and silver(I) oxide respectively.

Results and Discussion

The cinnamylphenols (1-4) on subjection to intramolecular oxypalladation reaction (PdCl₂, CuCl₂, O₂) yield the benzofurans (5-8) (Scheme 1). Thus, intramolecular version of the Wacker reaction provides an alternate route to heterocyclic compounds keeping in view the proposed in vivo formation of benzofurans by the loss of terminal three carbon atoms from a γ,γ -dimethylal-

lyl grouping followed by the construction of the furan ring from the remaining two carbon atoms⁴.

In contrast, the *ortho*-cinnamylphenol (4) elaborates a yellow colored compound, the *ortho*-vinylquinone methide (9) on treatment with silver(I)

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|---|---|---|---|
| 1 | R ¹ , R ³ , R ⁴ = H, R ² = OH | 5 | R ¹ , R ³ , R ⁴ = H, R ² = OH |
| 2 | R ¹ , R ² = OH, R ³ , R ⁴ = H | 6 | R ¹ , R ² = OH, R ³ , R ⁴ = H |
| 3 | R ² , R ⁴ = OH, R ¹ , R ³ = H | 7 | R ² , R ⁴ = OH, R ¹ , R ³ = H |
| 4 | R ¹ , R ⁴ = H, R ² , R ³ = OCH ₂ O | 8 | R ¹ , R ⁴ = H, R ² , R ³ = OCH ₂ O |

Scheme 1

oxide in methylene chloride. The colored intermediate is transformed to the flav-3-ene (10) on refluxing in benzene. Surprisingly, the phenols (1-3) are found to be non-reactive under these conditions. The observed lack of change can perhaps be attributed to the presence of an additional hydroxyl group.

Silver(I) oxide catalysis of eugenol (11) and isoeugenol (12): In order to compare the preferred mode of oxidation of *ortho*- and *para*-alkenylphenols, the behaviour of eugenol (11) and isoeugenol (12) towards silver(I) oxide have been studied. Eugenol (11) when reacted with silver(I) oxide in methylene chloride at ambient temperature gives the *ortho*-vinylquinone methide (13). The formation of 13 is ascertained by converting the same to 2-methoxy-4-(3-methoxy-1-propenyl)phenol (14) using methanol and catalytic amounts of acid (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Isoeugenol (12) serves as a model for the biogenesis of lignin related dimers during the enzymatic oxidation and dye-sensitised photo-oxidation and therefore has been chosen as the substrate for oxidation. Silver(I) oxide catalysed oxidation of isoeugenol in methylene chloride yields an intense yellow coloured compound identified as the quinone methide (15).

The intermediate 15 on quenching with methanol in acid medium affords the 8.0.4' neolignan (16). The nucleophilic addition of ethanol and water on the quinone methide yields neolignans 17 and 18 respectively, thus offering a biomimetic synthesis of natural product, virolin (18) having antileukaemic properties. Oxidation of isoeugenol in benzene medium gives the aryldihydrobenzofuran, dehydrodiisoeugenol (19) in addition to the neolignan (16). Dehydrodiisoeugenol has been shown to possess antiplaque action against the carcinogenic bacterium, *Streptococcus mutans*⁵.

Conclusion: Quinone methides are important intermediates in the chemical oxidation of *ortho*- and *para*-alkenylphenols. While two-electron oxidation of *ortho*-cinnamylphenols leads to benzofurans, one-electron oxidation of an *ortho*-cinnamylphenol yields a flavene. Silver(I) oxide mediated oxidation of a *para*-alkenyl phenol results in C-C and C-O coupled products.

Experimental

Nmr spectra were recorded on a Varian VXR spectrometer (internal standard), mass spectra on a Shimadzu spectrometer (70 eV) and ir spectra on a Perkin-Elmer IR-681 spectrophotometer.

Cyclisation of trans-2-(3-phenyl-2-propenyl)phenols (1-4). *General procedure*: The *ortho*-cinnamylphenol (10 mmol) dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) was added to a mixture of palladium chloride (0.4 mmol), cupric chloride (1 mmol) and water (2 ml). The mixture was stirred in an oxygen atmosphere at 60° for 5 h. The solution was then extracted with ether, washed with water and dried with Na₂SO₄. Chromatography of the residue obtained over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (95 : 5) yielded the benzofuran.

6,7-Methylenedioxy-2-phenyl-1H-chromene (8) : was stirred at ambient temperature. Silver(I) oxide

A solution of the phenol (4; 2.54 g, 1 mmol) dissolved in methylene chloride (5 ml)

(4.6 g, 2 mmol) was then added and the mixture was stirred for 1 h. The solution was filtered through a celite pad and the solvent evaporated. The red solid obtained was dissolved in benzene (10 ml) and refluxed for 2 h. Benzene was then distilled off to yield a yellow viscous liquid, which crystallised on standing, (8; 2.03 g, 80%) m.p. 71°.

TABLE I-SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd no	ν_{\max} (cm ⁻¹)	δ	Mol formula (M ^t) (mol wt)
5	3 400, 1 640, 1 610, 1 480, 1 080	4 20 (s, Ar-CH ₂), 4 60 (bs, OH), 6 27 (s, C ₃ -H), 6 70-7 30 (m, ArH)	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ (224)
6	3 400, 1 610, 1 480, 1 220, 1 080	4 20 (s, Ar-CH ₂), 4 60 (bs, OH), 6 27 (s, C ₃ -H), 6 70 (d, C ₅ -H, / 8Hz), 6 80 (d, C ₁₋₄ , / 8Hz), 7 30-7 40 (m, ArH)	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃ (240)
7	3 380, 1 610, 1 480, 1 230, 1 070	4 21 (s, Ar-CH ₂), 4 80 (bs, OH), 6 30 (s, C ₃ -H), 6 40 (d, C ₄ -H, / 2 4Hz), 6 50 (d, C ₆ -H, / 2 4Hz), 6 90-7 20 (m, ArH)	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃ (240)
8	3 400, 1 610, 1 470, 1 220, 1 080	4 20 (Ar-CH ₂), 5 85 (s, O-CH ₂ -O), 6 30 (s, C ₃ -H), 6 40 (s, ArH), 6 60 (s, ArH), 6 70-6 90 (m, ArH)	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ (252)
10	3 460, 1 640, 1 610, 1 480, 1 380, 1 230, 1 180, 940	5 72 (dd, C ₃ -H, / 9 0, 3 5Hz), 5 85 (dd, C ₂ -H, / 3 5, 1 5Hz), 5 89 (s, OCH ₂), 6 43 (s, ArH), 6 46 (dd, C ₄ -H, / 9 0, 1 5Hz), 6 54 (s, ArH), 7 30-7 60 (m, ArH)	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₃ (252)
14	3 480, 1 640, 1 610	3 38 (s, CH ₂ O-CH ₃), 3 89 (s, Ar-OCH ₃), 4 07 (d, CH=CH ₂), 5 70 (s, OH), 6 15 (m, C ₂ -H), 6 50 (d, / 15Hz, C ₁ -H), 6 86 (ArH)	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₃ (194)
16	3 520, 1 635, 1 610, 1 470, 1 380, 1 270, 960	1 30 (d, -O-C-CH ₃), 1 80 (d, CH-CH ₃), 3 40 (s, C ₇ -OCH ₃), 3 85, 3 89 (s, O-CH ₃), 5 20 (s, OH), 6 50 (m, C ₈ -H), 6 70 (d, C ₇ -H, / 15Hz), 6 80-7 10 (m, ArH)	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ O ₅ (358)
19	3 470, 1 635, 1 610	1 40 (d, C ₈ -CH ₃), 1 80 (d, CH=CH ₃), 3 40 (m, C ₈ -H), 3 80, 3 90 (s, OCH ₃), 5 10 (d, / 8Hz, C ₇ -H), 5 60 (s, OH), 6 04-6 18 (m, CH=CH ₃), 6 36 (d, / 15Hz, C ₁ -H), 6 80 (m, ArH)	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄ 326

Silver(I) oxide mediated oxidation. General procedure : A solution of the alkenylphenol (1 mmol) in dry methylene chloride (10 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature. Silver(I) oxide (2 mmol) was then added to it and the reaction continued for 1 h. The resulting yellow coloured solution was filtered through a pad of celite and the solvent distilled off. To the residue, benzene (5 ml), alcohol (3 ml) and *p*-TSA (10 mg) were added and the solution was stirred for 1 h. Evaporation of the solvent left a residue which was chromatographed on silica gel column and eluted with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (96 : 4) to yield the product (Table 1).

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References

- O R GOTTLIEB, *Fortsch Chem Org, Naturst.*, 1987, 1 35
- L L LANDUCCI and J RAI PH, *J Org Chem*, 1982, 47, 3486
- M IYER, D N RILE and G K TRIVEDI, *Tetrahedron Lett*, 1989, 7589
- A MUSTAFA, "Benzofurans", Wiley, New York, 1974
- M IIATTORI, S. HADA, A WATAHIKI, H IHARA, Y Z SHU, N KAKIUCHI and T MIZUNI, *Chem Pharm Bull*, 1986, 34, 3885

